
**< WITH A RULER AND A COMPASS >
AS THE RESTRICTIVE BASE - BECAME A REALITY
THE SOLUTION OF THE ANCIENT
UNSOLVED GREEK PROBLEMS**

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Abstract

a... The Unsolvability of the Three famous Ancient Greek Problems—Doubling the Cube, Trisecting the Angle, and Squaring the Circle -- **Stands on the Base justification** of the **Algebraic Field Theory (specifically GaloisTheory)** and the **Theory of Constructible Numbers**, which were developed in the 19th century.

b... The Greeks often used other **Techniques (like Conic sections or Mechanical tools)** to Solve these Problems, But **their self-imposed "Euclidean"** constraint, with a **Ruler and a Compass**, (straightedge and compass) made these Specific Problems impossible to solve.

c... In the Published Articles [123],[124],[126] , it is **clearly evident** that the Solution of the Ancient , Unsolved Greek Problems, using a **Ruler and a Compass** , as the constraint has been set by Euclid] , **Has Become Possible**, and is in the Critique of Both , **Human Logic Thinking and , The Artificial Intelligence** when it uses **The Path of Knowledge** to the Truths of Nature, and which is the **Dialectic Logic** of Euclidean Geometry .

d... From the Published Articles [123], [124], [126], All Steps Follow the Restrictions set by Euclid which are **< By A Ruler and a Compass >**

In the New Article [125] the Proof is repeated, Both of the Squaring of the circle and the Doubling of the Cube using only a Ruler and a Compass, as well as the Bellow-motion of the Photon with The Photon`s Cloning Method.

1.. Quadrature. [124] = Fig ,2-4

STEP-1 \Rightarrow On CA Segment as diameter , is drawn the circle (E , EC = EA) from center E , **the CA with a Ruler and circle (E , EC= EA) with a Compass.**

STEP-2 \Rightarrow On 2,AC Segment Draw circle (C , CP = CA) and from centers A , A' , Draw the circles (A , AA') , (A' = A'A) Intersected at Point P' , and Draw P'C Segment Intersecting the circle (C, CP) at Point P where issues **CP \perp CA . With a Ruler Draw CP Segment as diameter , and from the center E' with a Compass the circle (E' , E'C = E'P) . Let Point O be the center of AP .**

STEP-3 \Rightarrow From mid-Point O of the Hypotenuse AP as center , Draw the circle (O, OA= OP = OC) and **with a Ruler Complete the Squares , OCBA,OCB'P . On Perpendicular diameters OB , OB' and from Points B , B' Draw with a Compass \rightarrow The Conjugate ircles , (B, BE=EC) , (B' , B'E'=E'C) respectively intersecting the (E, EC) , (E' , E'P) circles at the Points **R , R'** , respectively,**

STEP-4 \Rightarrow From Points R , R' , Draw **with a Ruler** the line Segment ,**R R'** ,which Intersects the Diameter **COC'** at Poind **G** , and **with a Compass** , **OG'= OG**

STEP-5 \Rightarrow From Point **P** Draw **with a Ruler** the **PG'** line , intersecting the two circles (**O , OA**) , (**E' , E'P**) at Points **N , H** , respectively.

STEP-6 \Rightarrow Draw **with a Ruler** the line NA so that its extension intersects the circle (E , EA) at Point M and Draw **with a Ruler** Segments CM , CH . and Complete Quadrilateral CMNH , [*which is The Circles - System*] . Draw **with a Ruler** the line NP , so that its extension intersects the circle (E' , E'P) at Point N' , and Draw **with a Ruler** the Segments CM' , CH and Complete Quadrilateral CM'N'H , [*which is The Anti circles – System*] .

STEP-7 \Rightarrow It was shown that , By using a Ruler and a Compass Only , **the Quadrilaterals CMNH , CM'N'H are Squares** and that , **CMNH = [CM]² = π .[EC]² & CM'N'H = [CM']² = π .[EC']² and from $\pi . [EC]² \equiv CMNH = [CM]² then $\pi \equiv \frac{CMNH}{(EC)^2} \dots o.e.d.$$**

STEP-8 \Rightarrow For the Bellow-Motion and from Common Point R , the motion of circle (E , EC) Becomes from the Tangential velocity $\vec{C}_T = \vec{c} = RO$ which Passes from Point O . The tangential velocity $\vec{C}_T = RO$ on the circular Path is Balanced and Maintained by the Centripetal component \vec{C}_R . The Tangential velocity Vector $\vec{C}_T = \vec{RO}$ is analyzed to the Horizontal and to the Vertical velocities \vec{V}_x , \vec{V}_y . From the Geometrical Asymmetry of circles [B,BE] , [O,OA] , the Birefringence of \vec{RO} in Axis CC' is the **Path at Point G'** for both $\vec{V}_x , \vec{V}_y = \vec{RG}$ acting Perpendicularly so that (RG) = (R'G) \perp CC' . **Since GO = OG' motion is transferred at Point G' ,**
OR

The Velocity Vector $\vec{C}_T \equiv \vec{RO}$ Strikes at Point O , ACTS at Point G' , of the axis , within the Axis CC' , as \vec{V}_x , And Perpendicular , as \vec{V}_y , to This Axis with the Rotation Angle $G' \hat{P} O = 2\pi / r^2$ radians $\rightarrow C' \hat{P} O = 45^\circ$

With the Bellow-Motion , $C' \hat{P} O = 45^\circ$, Photon carries the **Herpolhode Energy = $\vec{c} . \pi . [EC]²$** into **Polhode Half-Circle Energy Store** , and into the **Anti-Polhode Half - Circle Energy Store** . **The Vector [$\vec{V}_x = OG'$] = Polhode = $\vec{c} . \pi . [EC]²$, carries the Twisted Energy in axis **COC'** , and creates the **Bellow motion of****

the Axis , denoting the **Electric – Field E** .

The Vector $[\vec{V}_y = G \cdot P] = \text{Anti-Polhode} = \bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [E \cdot C]^2$, carries the **Pushed Energy on CM`N`H - Square** and creates the **Storage** , denoting the **Magnetic – Field M** , of the **Electromagnetic Waves E ,M** . and thus is Photon Electromagnetic-Waves , where $E \perp M$,

Feom-[124], Show that Quadrilaterals CMNH , CM`N`H` are Squares ,
and that $CMNH = [CM]^2 = \pi \cdot [EC]^2$ & $CM`N`H` = [CM`]^2 = \pi \cdot [EC`]^2$

THE - PROOF :

- a...Because the Point M is located on the circle (E , EC) of Diameter CA , therefore angle $\widehat{CMA} = 90^\circ$ and $CM \perp MA \perp MN$.
- b...Because the Point N is located on the circle (O , OA) of Diameter AP , therefore angle $\widehat{MNP} = 90^\circ$ and $PN \perp NA \perp NM$.
- c...Because the Point H is located on the circle (E` , E`C) of Diameter CP , therefore angle $\widehat{CHP} = 90^\circ$ and since angle $\widehat{CHN} = 180^\circ - 90^\circ = 90^\circ$ then $NH \perp HC$.
- d...Because on Quadrilateral CMNH , the angle $\widehat{MCH} = 360^\circ - 270^\circ = 90^\circ$, therefore Quadrilateral CMNH is an Orthogonal-Quadrilateral . Since also the Right-Triangles CMA , CHP on Equal Diameters CA , CP , have their Sides CM , CH Perpendicular each other are also Equals and Side $CM = CH$. **Since Quadrilateral CMNH is an Orthogonal - Quadrilateral with Equal Sides Therefore is SQUARE. o.e.δ.**

Conclusions :

- 1...Any Point M on arc of (E , EC) circle , between the Points , B , A , forms a Square CMNH on **The Circles** → **System** , and the Square , CM`N`H` , on **The-Idol** → **The Anti – System** Both on the → **2-Vectors , 3-Poles Rotating Squares Mechanism** ← Since squares CBAO , CAC`P , belong to circles (E , EC) , (O,OC = OA) , therefore This Mechanism carries the Area $\pi \cdot [EC]^2$ of (E , EC) circle , to circle (O,OC = OA) . Since the inscribed circle to Square CAC`P is equal to the circle (E , EC) , therefore this Mechanism carries also all Properties of the circle from Point B to A . Since also square $CAC`P = 2 \cdot CBAO$, then $\pi \cdot [OC]^2 = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot [EC]^2$. **i.e. The Mechanism carries circle (E , EC) to circle (O,OC = OA) of Double Area .**
- 2...The Circles Anti-circles System are Equal and Placed Symmetrical on Common axis .
- 3...The Rolling of Point M on circle (E , EC) means Point M is moving on the arc having → Radius of Curvature $ME \perp MT$ the Tangent ← at Point M .
- 4.. It was Proved [44] and from Analysis , that when Point B is Rolling on the circumference of circle (E,EC)–[say **Point M**] and MA line extended at Point N of circle (O,OC= OA) by Joining PN which intersects the circle (E` , E`C) at Point H , **Then** the formed Square CMNH is in the circle (O,OC = OA) .
- 5.. When Point M is **on Point B** , common to circle (E , EC) and to center of circle (B , BE) , BA line extended at Point A of circle (O,OC= OA) and Joining PA and intersecting the circle (E` , E`C) at Point O , The formed Square CBAO is the square in circle (E , EC). **Since the Conjugate circle (B , BE) is constant and Unmovable** and the Only motion is the Rotational-motion , **Therefore This circle (B , BE) carries the Properties of this circle** say the Area of circle $\pi \cdot [EB]^2$ in the circle (E , EC) and issues $\pi \cdot [EB]^2 = \pi \cdot [EC]^2$.
- 6.. When Point M is **on Point R** , common to circles (E , EC) , (B , BE) , **Then** CR NR HR is also a Square in the circle (O,OC = OA) . This **Conjugate circle** carries the Properties of circle (B , BE) say ,**The Inscribed Square CBAO** which is equal to that of circle and the **Area of circle = $\pi \cdot [EC]^2$** in the circle (O,OC= OA), **But How ? ⇒ In-Reverse.← To Show that at Point R , , Common to circles (E , EC) , (B , BE) , , , , ⇒**

The Conjugate circle (B , BE) , Stores its Properties to the Half of circle (O,OC= OA).

Since OB is Diameter in circle (E , EO) and angle $\widehat{BRO} = 90^\circ$, therefore $RB \perp RO$.
 At this Point R the Radius of Curvature **RB , is Perpendicular to AT-tangent $\rightarrow RO$**
 and Passes from Point O . Since Geometrical - **Vector RO** is analysed to $RG \perp COC'$
 and GO in COC' then the Right-Triangles GAO , $OG'P$ are Equal because their interior
 alternate angles $G\widehat{AO} = G'\widehat{PO}$, and so exists $OG = OG'$.

By Extending PG' on circles $(E', E'C)$, $(O,OC= OA)$ occupy the H , N , Points and
 then Extending NA to M Point on (E , EC) circle , **Then CMNH is Square . i.e.**
 The area of circle $(B , BE) \equiv (E , EC)$, is Transported to the Half of circle (O , OC) , as

$$\pi \cdot [EC]^2 \equiv CMNH = [CM]^2 \quad \& \quad \pi \equiv \frac{CMNH}{(EC)^2} \quad \dots\dots\dots \text{o.e.}\delta.$$

7.. When Point M is **on Point A** , common to circles (E , EC) , (O , OC) , **Then CAC'P**
 is also a Square in the circle $(O,OC = OA)$. **At this Point A** the Radius of Curvature
AE , is Perpendicular (\perp) to AC' \rightarrow AT-tangent , which Passes from Point C' , **i.e.**
 The area of circle $(B , BE) \equiv (E , EC)$, is Transported to the Halve of circle (O , OC) .

8.. When we say that Point M is on the **Arc BA** of the circle (E , EC) , then according to the
 Principles of Euclidean Geometry , this Point is considered to be **Without Position** , and
 for a Straight-Line Segment , it is also **Without Direction** . This happens because in the
 Euclidian Geometry Between any Two adjacent Points exist Infinite , ∞ , Points .
The Position is Specified Only by their **Common Point R** , of intersection of the
 Conjugate Circle $(B , BE=EC)$ and (E , EC) , and **The Direction is Defined** by the
 Tangent **RO** , of the Conjugate Circle at their Common Point R .

**This commitment Determines for us , The Unique Position of Common Point R of
 that Square CMNH on arc BA , which Area is Equal to that of the circle (E , EC) .**

The exact Numeric Magnitude of number , π , may be found only by numeric
 calculations.[44] . All magnitudes exist on the **< Plane Formation Mechanism of
 the first dimensional unit AC >** as geometrical elements consisting , **the Steady Formulation** ,
 (The Plane System of the Isosceles Right-angle triangle ACP with the three Circles on the sides
) and **the moving and Changeable Formulation of the twin , System-Image** , (This Plane
 Perpendicular System of Squares , Anti-squares is such that , *the Work Produced in a between
 closed area to be equal to zero*) .

Starting from this logic of correlation upon Unit , we can control *Resemblance Ratio* and
 construct all the Regular Polygons on the unit Circle as this is shown in the case of squares .
 On this **System** of these three circles [124]-F.2 (The Plane Procedure Mechanism which is a
 Constant System) is created also , a *continues* and , an *Ucontinues* Symmetrical Formation ,
 the changeable System of the Regular Polygons , and
 their **Image** (Changeable System of Regular anti-Polygons) the **Idol** , as much
 this in **Space** and also in **Time** , and was proved that in this Constant System
*the Rectilinear motion of the Changeable Formation is Transformed into a
 twin and Symmetrically axial-centrifugal Pole rotation (this is the motion on System)*.

The conservation of the Total Impulse and Momentum , as well as the conservation of the
 Total Energy in this Constant System with all properties included , exists in this Empty Space
 of the un-dimensional Point Unit mechanism.

All the forgoing referred can be shown (maybe Presented) with a Ruler and a Compass , or
 can be seen , live , on any Personal Computer , on Dr.Geo machine .

The theorem of *Hermit-Lindeman* that number , π , is not Algebraic , is based on the theory of
 Constructible numbers and number fields (*on Number Analysis*) and Not on the **< Euclidean
 Geometrical Origin-Euclid-Logic on Unit Elements Basis >**

The mathematical reasoning (*the Method*) is based on the Restrictions imposed to seek the
 solution **< i.e. with a Ruler and a Compass >** .

By extending Euclid logic of Units on the Unit circle *to unknown and now Proved Geometrical unit elements*, thus the settled age-old question for the unsolved Problems is now approached and continuously standing solved. All Mathematical interpretation and the Relative Philosophical reflections based on the theory of the Non-Solvability must Properly Revised. (markos 30/10/2015)

Application in Physics :

From math theory of Elasticity , Cauchy equations of **Stresses** in three Dimensions are ,

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yx}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zx}}{\partial z} + X = 0, \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial z} + Y = 0, \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \sigma_z}{\partial z} + Z = 0$$

where are ,

$\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$ = The Principal stresses in x, y, z Axis ,
 $\tau_{xy}, \tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}$ = The Shear-stresses in xy, xz, yz Plane,

X, Y, Z = The components of external forces and of **Strain** , $\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} = 0, \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0$

and $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = 0$ where $u = u(y, z) \rightarrow$ are the Deformation components,
the displacements in , y, z axis .

$v = c \ x \ z$ = The Rotation on z , axis

$w = -c \ x \ y$ = Anti-rotation in y , axis .

Applying above equations on an orthogonal section of a solid , then exist the differential equations of equilibrium , and for the Boundary conditions is found that , the Stress function is satisfying the equations , $\frac{\partial \tau_{yx}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zx}}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial \gamma_{yx}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \gamma_{zx}}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = 0 \dots (1)$ and the Boundary conditions on Solid's surface ,

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} dz - \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} dy + y.dy + z.dz = 0 \dots (2)$$

where , $\gamma_{xy}, \gamma_{xz}, \gamma_{yz}$ = the Slip components where is ,

$\gamma_{xy} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}$. Equations show that the Resultant Shear-stress at the Boundary is directed along

the Tangent to the Boundary and that , the Stress function $u = u(yz)$ must be Constant along the Boundary of the cross section . **i.e. each cross section on x , axis is Rotated as a Disk in its Plane** , from which Points follow relation $u = u(yz)$ and since Stress function are constant , then from equation (2) $y.dy + z.dz = 0$, or $y^2 + z^2 = \text{constant}$ meaning that , **A Cross-section under Stress Stays Plane only in Circle circumference , or a Plane Space , under ENERGY Stress , remains**

Flat only when the Plane Becomes a circle , i.e . The Photon carries the **Herpolhode** Energy = $\bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [EC]^2$ of the **Conjugate-circle** $\equiv (B, BE=EC)$ into the **Polhode** Half-Circle Energy Store , and into the **Anti-Polhode** Half - Circle Energy Store . **Thus Photon follows the Plane - Mould – Mechanism which is the Squaring of the Herpolhode - circle.**

The same is seen in Laplace's equation $\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} \equiv \nabla^2 u = 0$ which is termed a Harmonic function.

Placing $\nabla^2 u = 0$ in Both Parts of the equation of the circle , becomes Identity and $\nabla^2 u \cdot (y^2 + z^2) = \nabla^2 u \cdot (c)$, **or any Monad = Quaternion , consisted of the Real Part the Plane Space , and under Energy Stress the Imaginary Part** \equiv the **Herpolhode** Energy = $\bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [EC]^2$, **remains in Flat only when the Plane Becomes a circle , i.e. The Energy-Space discrete continuum follows the Extrema E-geometry Mould , π , which is the Squaring of the Herpolhode - circle.** If Potential Energy is zero then Vector \bar{r} is on the Surface indicating the conjugate function. [49].

In Electricity , when an Electric current flows through a Conductor , then a Transverse circular Electromagnetic field is Produced around itself which follows the Vectors-cross-Product Plane **Mould – Mechanism which is the Squaring of the Herpolhode-circle** , $\pi \cdot |H|^2$. (markos 20 / 05 / 2026)

Figure -2- The Steps for Squaring the circles (E , EC = EA = EO = EB) , and (E' , E'C = E'P = E'B' = E'O) , Through Geometric - Requirements , Using < A Ruler and A Compass > as this was first Posed by the Ancient Greeks .

Figure-4- The Total Energy $2 \cdot E = \text{Spin} = \vec{S} = \vec{w} \cdot \vec{B} = \vec{c} \cdot \vec{B} = \vec{c} \cdot \left| \frac{\vec{B}}{r} \right|$, and $\vec{c} = \vec{c}_P = \left| \frac{2 \cdot r \cdot \vec{E}}{\vec{B}} \right|$
The Velocity of Photon \vec{c}_P is analyzed to Centripetal $\vec{c}_K \equiv \vec{RB}$, Tangential $\vec{c}_T \equiv \vec{RO}$

2.. Duplication. [126] = Fig ,1-2-3

STEP-1 \Rightarrow On CA Segment as diameter Draw **with a Compass** circle (B',B'C=B'A) and circle (C, CB'=CP') where P' is the Point of Intersection of AC Produced **with a Ruler** . and from centers B', P', Draw **with a Compass** the two circles (B',B'P') and (P',P'B') Intersected at Point C', and Draw **with a Ruler** C'C Segment Intersecting circle (C, CB') at Point B where issues **CB \perp CA = 2.CB**

STEP-2 \Rightarrow On AB Hypotenuse Segment Draw **with a Compass** the circle (O,OC=OA=OB), from Mid-Point O and from Point C, Draw (C,CA=CD'=CP').

STEP-3 \Rightarrow Form **with a Ruler** and on Straight line BP', the Diameter BA'=BA and Draw **with a Compass** the circle (O',O'B = O'A'), and Draw also Arc AP of the circle (A', A'A = A'P), where Point P lies on line BP'.

STEP-4 \Rightarrow Draw **with a Compass** the circle (K, KB = KP), from the Mid-Point K of the Line-Sector BP, which intersects the line AD' Produced at Point D. Draw **with a Ruler** line DB intersecting the circle (O, OB) at Point E, and Draw the Diameter EE'. of the circle (O, OB).

STEP-5 \Rightarrow Complete **with a Ruler** the Quadrilaterals PAED, PE'BD.

STEP-6 \Rightarrow It was shown that, By using a Ruler and a Compass Only, that Quadrilaterals PAED, PE'BD are Rectangular Parallelograms, and On the Right-angled Triangles PAD & PBD, valids $[CD]^3 = 2.[CP]^3$.

STEP-7 \Rightarrow For Photon's SPIN Vector equal to $\bar{X} = OG'$, and By using a Ruler and a Compass Only, is found a Cloning Vector Z, such that $\rightarrow |Z|^3 = 2. |X|^3$. \leftarrow Fig- 2, 3-

STEP-8 \Rightarrow FORM ON \Rightarrow { The 2-Vectors, 3-Poles Rotating Squares Mechanism }, of the Equal Vectors, By using a Ruler and a Compass Only, The UNID Monad [CMNH]² equal to [CM]² and equal to Energy-Circle = $\pi.[CA/2]^2$, and ON The UNIT – VELOCITY – VECTOR \rightarrow { \bar{V}_x Vector \equiv Square CMNH $\equiv \pi.[CA/2]^2 = [CP]^2 \equiv \pi.[CA/2]^2$ } \leftarrow & FORM The 2-Right Triangles, PAD, PBD, from { The 2-Vectors, 2-Poles Rotating Squares Mechanism }, On where valids the Duplication on the Unequal Vectors and The CUBES $[CP]^3 = 2.[CD]^3$, AND PLACE the Velocity-Vector $|\bar{V}_x| \equiv$ Vector X, IN CP and DEFINE the Vector |Z|. where For Vector |Z| valids $\rightarrow |Z|^3 = 2. |X|^3$ \leftarrow and This is, The Quantum-Cloning of Photons.

From-[126], THE PROOF :

- a).. The Point E of the circle (O, OA) forms the Right Angle AEB, because it lies on the diameter BA, of the circle. The angle AED = $180^\circ - 90^\circ = 90^\circ$,
- b).. Angle EDP = 90° because it lies on the diameter BP of the circle (K, KB = KP), Therefore the Angle PE'B = 90° is lying on the same diameter BP of the circle.
- c).. Because in the Quadrilateral PE'BD, the 3-angles, PE'B = E'BD = BDP = 90° , Therefore the Quadrilateral PE'BD of the circle (K, KB), is also a Rectangular Parallelogram, and thus line Segment PB' Passes through Point A.

- d).. It was Proved that the Angles $\widehat{AED} = \widehat{EDP} = \widehat{DPE} = 90^\circ$, Because they lie on the diameter **BP** of the circle (**K ,KB = KP**) , **Therefore** the Line **ED** is **Parallel** to **PE** .
- e).. Because the angle $\widehat{EDP} = 90^\circ$ and on the diameter **EP** of the circle , and Because the angle \widehat{PAE} lies on the same diameter **EP** of the circle , **Therefore** angle $\widehat{PAE} = 90^\circ$.
- f).. Since for the angles it holds that $\widehat{PAE} = \widehat{PEB} = 90^\circ$,Therefore the Rectangle **PAED** is Inside of **PEBD** , and Point **A** lies on **PE** .
- g).. On the Right Triangles **PAD** , **PBD** it is true , 1).. $[CP]^2 = CA.CD$ and 2).. $[CD]^2 = CP.CD$, Dividing we have $\frac{[CD]^2}{[CP]^2} = \frac{CP.CD}{CA.CD}$, and then after an Order $\frac{[CD]^3}{[CP]^3} = \frac{CD}{CA} = 2$.

h)..**The Method** Is Based on the **Theory of Parallels** , and is , [Thalis], (Figure-3-)
 Let **X** , a Line Segment Placed on the Perpendicular , **CP**, and , **A_x** , **D_z** Be the Sections of the Parallels , **P_{xy} - A_x** , **P_{xy} - D_z** , to which , **PA** , **PD** , respectively.
 In Similar Triangles , **CPD** , **CP_{xz} D_z** , The Ratios apply , ($\frac{C.D_z}{CD} = \frac{C.P_{xz}}{CP} = \frac{Z}{CD} = \frac{X}{CP}$.)
 and by Rearranging the Terms $\frac{Z}{X} = \frac{CD}{CP}$ -(h)- Since On the Mechanism **ACDP**, it holds

$$\frac{[X]^3}{[Z]^3} = 2$$

Therefore for -(h)- it holds also $\rightarrow \frac{[X]^3}{[Z]^3} = 2 \leftarrow$, **That is** ,,,,,

On the Mechanism , ACDP , The Straight line-Vector Z Has been found such that , The Cube of Z is Double that of X o.ε.δ.

Observation :

When the Obtained Point of **Application** , POSITION , of the Straight Segment **X** , is any POINT , then according to the Principles of Euclidean Geometry it is considered without **Position Magnitude** and **Direction** , This Geometric Indefiniteness of the Continuity of Points on Straight Line EXCLUDES at the Common Point **C** , of the 2-Segments , **X** , **Z** , and the **Direction** of this is **That , of the Maximum Perpendicular of the Mechanism PABD** of the Triangles , **PAD** & **PBD** .[Fig-2-]

Feom-[126] , THE MECHANICAL - METHOD FOR THE CLONING OF PHOTONS

THE - STEPS :

- 1.. Let the Photon`s **SPIN Vector** , Be equal to $\bar{X} = OG$, and to find a Cloning Vector **Z** , such that $\rightarrow [Z]^3 = 2 . [X]^3 . \leftarrow$ **Fig-2 , 3-**
- 2.. See Proof in [123] WHERE on the 2-Vectors , 3-Poles Rotating Squares Mechanism , A Point **M** on Arc - **BA** is Rolling on the circumference of circle (E,EC) , and the MA line extended at Point **N** of circle (O,OC= OA) by Joining PN , which intersects the circle E`E`C at Point **H** , Then the formed Square **CMNH** is in circle [O,OC= OA] AND WHEN **SPIN** $\equiv \tilde{B}$ of Photons is on Mechanism at the constant Point **B** , then its **Herpolhode** is the Circle [B , BE] and **Polhode** is the circle [O , OA] , where on B Point the motion is only the Spinn $\equiv \tilde{B} \equiv \bar{c} . \pi . [EC]^2$. This Quantity of Energy in **Herpolhode** Energy-circle is Stored in the [O , OA] Half -Part circle as **UNIT** Quantity = $\pi . [EC]^2$ of the **Total Energy** , which is The Curl-motion $\equiv \bar{c} . 2\pi . [EC]^2$.
- 3.. See Proof , for the Rolling of Point **B** on (E, EC) circle meaning \rightarrow Radius of Curvature **BE** \perp **BA** \leftarrow tangent , where $\overrightarrow{C_R}$, $\overrightarrow{C_T}$, are the two constitues of light velocity vector \bar{c} .
 i.e. $\bar{c} = \tilde{B} / \pi . [EC]^2$, $\bar{c}_p = \left| \frac{2.r.\tilde{E}}{B} \right|$ & The circle (B , BE) carries the motion $\bar{c} . \pi . [EB]^2$ in the circle (E , EC) , where from relation $|\overrightarrow{C_R}| \equiv \sigma . \Phi$ issues $\Rightarrow \bar{c} . \pi . [EC]^2 \equiv \bar{c} . \pi . [EB]^2$.

- 4.. See the Proof ,where **To Transfer** the Properties of Herpolhode , of the Conjugate circle (B,BE) to the circle (E , EC) , is required the existence of at least **One Common Point** Between them , **The Position also** is by their **Common Point R** , of intersection of the Conjugate Circle (B,BE=EC) and (E,EC) , **And Direction is Defined** by the Tangential Velocity $\vec{C}_T \equiv \text{Tangent RO}$, of the Conjugate Circle at Common Point R .
- 5.. See the Proof , that **When SPIN** $\equiv \vec{B}$ of **Photons** is on Common- Point **R** ,the Tangential Velocity \vec{C}_T **Passes** from Center O , is Analyzed into Components \vec{V}_x, \vec{V}_y is **ACTING** at Point **G`** , Forming The **UNIT Square CMNH** = $[\text{CM}]^2$ AND Equal to Energy-Circle = $\pi \cdot [\text{CA}/2]^2$. **THE** \vec{V}_x , Component **ACTS** at Point **G`** , **Tortionally** through Poles A ,O , **Forming ON** The **MOULD** of The 2-Right Triangles , **PAD , PBD** \rightarrow **The Mechanism of Dublication** $[\text{CP}]^3 = 2 \cdot [\text{CD}]^3 \leftarrow$ Where The \vec{V}_x Vector \equiv Square CMNH $\equiv \pi \cdot [\text{CA}/2]^2 = [\text{CP}]^2$, which **PUSHES** the \vec{V}_x Vector-Energy **INTO** The CUBE $[\text{CP}]^3 = |\vec{V}_x|^3$,
- 6.. **FORM ON** \Rightarrow { The 2-Vectors , 3-Poles Rotating Squares **Mechanism** } , of the Equal Vectors , **The UNID Monad** $[\text{CMNH}]^2$ equal to $[\text{CM}]^2$ and equal to Energy-Circle = $\pi \cdot [\text{CA}/2]^2$, and **ON** The **UNIT – VELOCITY – VECTOR** \rightarrow { \vec{V}_x Vector \equiv Square CMNH $\equiv \pi \cdot [\text{CA}/2]^2 = [\text{CP}]^2 \equiv \pi \cdot [\text{CA}/2]^2$ } \leftarrow
FORM The 2-Right Triangles , **PAD , PBD** , from { The 2-Vectors , 2-Poles Rotating Squares **Mechanism** } , On where valids the Dublication on the Unequal Vectors and The CUBES $[\text{CP}]^3 = 2 \cdot [\text{CD}]^3$, **AND PLACE** the Velocity-Vector $|\vec{V}_x| \equiv \text{Vector X}$, IN **CP** and **DEFINE** the Vector $|\text{Z}|$.

For Vector $|\text{Z}|$ valids $\rightarrow |\text{Z}|^3 = 2 \cdot |\text{X}|^3 \leftarrow$ and This is Done ,

The Quantum-Cloning of Photons.

- 7.. **When the Electric-Field E** , of **Photons** is on Common- Point **R** , The Tangential-Velocity \vec{C}_T **Passes** from Center O , is Analyzed into Components \vec{V}_x, \vec{V}_y and **ACTS** at Point **G`** , forming The **UNIT Square CMNH** = $[\text{CM}]^2$ and which is Equal to the Energy - Circle = $\pi \cdot [\text{CA}/2]^2$.
THE \vec{V}_x , Component **ACTS** at Point , **G`** **Tortionally** through the 2-Poles A , O , and **Forms ON** The **MOULD** of The 2-Right Triangles **PAD , PBD** \rightarrow **The Mechanism of Dublication** $[\text{CP}]^3 = 2 \cdot [\text{CD}]^3 \leftarrow$ Where The \vec{V}_x Vector \equiv Square CMNH $\equiv \pi \cdot [\text{CA}/2]^2 = [\text{CP}/2]^2$, **PUSHES** the \vec{V}_x Vector-Energy **INTO** The CUBE , $[\text{CP}]^3 = |\vec{V}_x|^3$,
i.e.

The Velocity-Vector , $|\vec{V}_x|$, IS Placed on **CG` Direction** through Point **G`** , and **ACTS** Rotationally By Polarization \equiv **Spinning** \equiv **Tortionally Curled** through the O ,A **2-Poles**. and **FORMS** \rightarrow **The Mechanism of Dublication** \leftarrow On which The **UNIT Energy-Square** $[\text{CMNH}] = |\vec{V}_x|^3 = [\text{CP}]^3$.. On This Mechanism the Unit Energy is Doubled , and this from the Energy-Curl-motion of Cube $[\text{CP}]^3$ & $\rightarrow [\text{CD}]^3 = 2 \cdot [\text{CP}]^3 \leftarrow$

AND THUS IS DONE ,

THE QUANTUM CLONING MOULD OF PHOTONS o.e.d.

This Problem follows the three Dimensional , **Dialectic logic of Ancient Greek** , Αναξίμανδρος, [« τό μή Ον , Ον γίνεσθαι » The Non-existent Exists when is done , [6-13]

[The Non - existent Becomes and never is] , where **the Geometrical magnitudes**, have a **linear relation** (the continuous Analogy on Segments) **in all Spaces as , in one in two in three dimensions , as this happens to the Compatible Coordinate Systems .**

The Structure of Euclidean Geometry is such [6] that it is a Compact Logic where **Non - Existent** is found everywhere , and **Existence** , *monads* ,is found and is done everywhere . In Euclidean geometry Points do not exist , but their Position and correlation is doing geometry The Universe cannot be created , Because it is continuously becoming and never is [9]

According to Euclidean Geometry ,and since the Position of Points (*empty Space*) creates the geometry and Spaces , Zenon Paradox is the first concept of Quantization . [15]

In terms of Mechanics , Spaces Mould happen through ,*Mould of Doubling the Cube* , where for any monad $ds = CA$ and analogous to CD , the Volume or The cube of segment CD is the double the volume of CA cube , or monad $CD^3 = 2.CA^3$. This is one of the basic Geometrical Euclidean Geometry Moulds , which create the METERS of monads which \rightarrow **Linear** is the Segment $ds = CAx$, **Plane** is , π , the square $CMNH$ equal to the circle , and in **Space** is $\sqrt[3]{2}$ the volume CD^3 , in all Spaces , Anti-spaces and Sub -spaces of monads \leftarrow i.e. The Expanding square $AxExDzPxz$ is Quantized to AEDP Rectangle by Translation to Point D , and by Rotation through point B , (the Pole of rotation) . The Constructing relation between any segments X , Y is $\rightarrow (CP)^3 = (CD)^3 . (BA / BE)$ as in F.2

Application in Physics :

The Electromagnetic waves are able to transmit Energy through a Vacuum (*empty space*) by storing their Energy Vector in an Standing Transverse Electromagnetic Dipole wave , and so considered completely Particle like , and in the transverse interference pattern to be considered as completely Wave , so the Same Quantity of Energy is as Intensity ,

Energy $I_d = \frac{\rho\pi^2c^3}{2\lambda^2}[\epsilon E^2 + \mu H^2]$ in volume $V = [\frac{4(w^2r^2)^3}{3\pi}]$ having mass \rightarrow **Particle Energy**

$I_d = (\frac{\rho.c}{2}).(wA_o)^2$ in Interference Pattern as \rightarrow **Wave**

This is the Wave-Particle duality unifying the classical Electromagnetic field and the Quantum Particle of light .Angular momentum of particles is \rightarrow Spin $= \frac{E}{w} = [\pm\bar{v}.s^2] / w = (r.s^2) = w^2r^3 = [wr]^3$ and , as Spin $= \frac{h}{\pi} = 2.[wr]^3$, or **Energy Space quantity** wr ,

is doubled and becomes the Space quantity $\frac{h}{\pi} = 2.[wr]^3$,

The above relation of Spin shows the deep relation between Mechanics and Egeometry , where in the tiny **Gravity-cave** of $r = 10^{-62}$ m , the Energy -Volume-quantity $[wr]$ in cave , **is Doubled and is Quantized in Planck`s - cave Space quantity** as , $(\frac{h}{\pi}) = \text{Spin} = 2.[wr]^3$ in $r = 10^{-35}$ m i.e.

The Energy Space quantity , wr , is Quantized , and Becomes the New Space quantity , $h / \pi = 2.[wr]^3$, **Doubled** , following the Euclidean Space-mould of *Duplication of the Cube by changing frequency* , in tiny Sphere volume $V = (4\pi/3).[wr/2]^3$. Also ,

Since $w = E / [h/2\pi] = m.c^2 / [h/2\pi] = 2\pi.mc^2 / h = 2r.s^2 = 4.r^3.w^2$, since $s = 2wr$, then the mass $m = 2 \frac{(wr)^3}{c^2} = \frac{2}{c^2} (wr)^3$, is Doubled as above with Space-mould and , **is what is called**

conversion factor mass , **m** , and it is an Index of the Energy Changes .

All Energy magnitudes from , $0 \rightarrow \infty$, **Deposit in the same Space** , *Resonance* ,

By changing frequency . The Conservation of Energy in Caves and in Atoms Compounds have been widely Analyzed and Proofed in Prior Articles [106],[118] , where in Mechanics and Physics is generally followed the Theory of Vibrations for Actions. [127]

THE DUBLICATION OF THE CUBE ON TWO VECTORS

VECTOR, $CA \perp CB$,
& $CB = 2.CA$,
or $CB / CA = 2$.

DRAW HYPOTENUSE AB , OF
CON-CIRCLE $\{O, OC = OA\}$ & DRAW
THE CIRCLE $\{C, CA=CP'=CD'\}$ WITH
THE DIAMETER $AD' = CB = 2.CA$.

DRAW ON CB , THE EQUAL **CON-CIRCLE**,
 $\{O', O'A' = O'B'\}$, COMPLETE SQUARE
 $[AB'D'P']$ & FORM THE NEW POSITION
OF POINT P' AT P , WHERE $A'A = A'P$

$$[DC]^3 / [PC]^3 = CB / CA = 2$$

DRAW THE CIRCLE $\{K, KB=KP\}$ ON DIAMETER BP , WHICH INTERSECTS THE LINE AD' AT POINT D , AND DRAW LINE DB INTERSECTING THE CIRCLE $\{O, OB\}$. AT POINT E . FORM THE DIAMETER EOE' OF CIRCLE $\{O, OA\}$ & COMPLETE THE TWO FOUR-SIDED , $PAED$, $PE'BD$.

SINCE $PD \perp PA$ & $AE \perp EB$. SO
ANGLE $\{APD = AEB = AED = 90^\circ\}$
& SINCE LIE ON DIAMETER , AD ,
OF CIRCLE $\{C, CA=CD=CP=CE\}$
THEN $PAED$, $PE'BD$ ARE
RECTANGULAR-PARALLELOGRAM

THE QUICK-PROOF :
1..ON RIGHT-ANGLED TRIANGLES , PAD & PBD ,
ISSUES $[PC]^2 = [CA.CD]$ & $[DC]^2 = [CP.CB]$
2..BY-DIVISION $[DC]^2 / [PC]^2 = [CP.CB / CA.CD]$
And $[DC]^3 / [PC]^3 = CB / CA = 2$ **OEδ**

S-0

Figure-1-

The , 2-Vectors 2-Poles Rotating Rectangular Mechanism . where ,The Straight line Segment , $CB = 2.CA$, and $CB \perp CA$, and the circles $(O, OC = \frac{AB}{2})$. $(O', O'B = \frac{AB}{2})$,
On the Two Equal Diameters $BA = BA'$, of the Equal Hypotenuses , BA , BA' , and the 2-Poles at the Points A , B , valids on Triangles PAD & PBD Mechanism , which is $[CD]^3 = 2.[CP]^3$.
For any Vector X Placed on CP , is found on Direction CD through Point C . Vector Y .

THE MOULD FOR **DUBLICATION OF THE CUBE** $[CD]^3 = 2..[CP]^3$

VECTOR, $CA \perp CB$,
& $CB = 2.CA$,
or $CB / CA = 2$,

ANY VECTOR, X , FORMING THE ANGLE, ϕ , ON
DA-LINE-VECTOR, IS TRANSPORTED ON THE
2-VECTORS 2-POLES, MOULD AND MEASURED

1..ON RIGHT-ANGLED TRIANGLES, PAD & PBD ,
ISSUES $[PC] \approx [CA.CD]$ & $[DC] \approx [CP.CB]$
2..BY-DIVISION $[DC]^{1/2} / [PC] \approx [CP.CB / CA.CD]$

CUBES UNID-MONAD MOULD

ON TRIANGLE PAD AND
 $P_{xz}AxD_z$ ISSUES $Z/CD = X/CP$,
OR $Z : X = CD : CP$
SINCE $[CD]^3 = 2..[CP]^3$,
AND $[Z]^3 = 2..[X]^3$,
OR
 $Z^3 = 2..X^3$

Figure-2-

In (1) .., The **MOULD** of The 2-Right Triangles PAD , PBD on where valids the
Dublication $[CP]^3 = 2..[CD]^3$. and for Any Segment X , to Be **Duplicated to Y** .
In (2) .., The Vector , X , is Placed on CP , **Direction** through Point C . The Parallels ,
($P_{xy} - A_x$) , ($P_{xy} - D_z$) , to which Determine the Points A_x , D_z , and such that ,
 $CD_z = |Z|$ and $C - P_{xy} = |X|$, where valids the Relation $\Rightarrow |Z|^3 = 2 . |X|^3$

THE **QUANTUM - CLONING** MOULD OF PHOTONS

THE ANGULAR MOMENTUM \bar{B} AS SPIN
 \bar{S} OF PHOTONS ON THE CONJUGATE CIRCLE
[$B, BE = EC$] OF -- 2-Vectors 3-Poles R-Mechanism --

THE ANGULAR MOMENTUM \bar{B} , AS
THE SPIN -- \bar{S} -- OF PHOTONS ON THE
2-Vectors 3-Poles Rotation- Mechanism -
BECOMES a)...THE UNIT - SQUARE =
 $CMNH = \pi . |AC/2|^2$ b)...THE UNIT-CUBE
= $|CP|^3 = |EB|^3$, AND c)...THE
CLONING - UNIT CUBE = $|CD|^3 = 2 . |EB|^3$

THE PROOF
> FROM Relation $Spin=S = \bar{v}.B/2 = \bar{c}.B/2r$
Then $\bar{c} = |2.r.S/B| = \sqrt{CT^2 + CR^2}$ AND
AT POINT R, $\bar{C}_T = \bar{R}O = \sqrt{V_x^2 + V_y^2}$
> AT Point R, $|C_T = \bar{R}O| = \sqrt{V_x^2 + V_y^2}$
Tangential Velocity $\bar{R}O$, ACTS AT Point
 G' , ... \bar{V}_x ON $\ll CC'$ Axis & $\bar{V}_y \perp$ ON CC' ...
PUSHING $CMNH$, UNIT-Energy, SQUARE
Forming THE TORSIONAL ANGLE
 $\phi = \phi = G' \bar{P}O = 2\pi/r^2$ Rads.
> FOR Point . G' AT C' , Torsional Angle
 $\phi = C' \bar{P}O = 2\pi / r^2 = 45^\circ$, which
is The Bellow Motion of Photon, AND
Energy-Square $CAC'P = CMNH \cdot CHH' M'$.

IN-(1)..THE SPIN { \bar{B} }=THE CIRCLE
FROM HERPOLHODE= $\{c.\pi . |EC|^2\}$, OF
PHOTONS, AND IS TRANSPORTED AS
VELOCITY $\bar{R}O = \sqrt{V_x^2 + V_y^2}$ & ACTS
AT POINT G' , ... \bar{V}_x INTO, CC' AXIS
AND \bar{V}_y , ONTO, CC' AXIS -
PUSHING $|CM| \approx CMNH$, UNIT-ENERGY,
SQUARE= $\pi . |AC/2|^2$, FORMING TORSIONAL
ANGLE $\phi = G' \bar{P}O = 2\pi/r^2$ Rads.

IN-(2)..THE VELOCITY VECTOR $\bar{A}B$
ACTS AT POINT B - WITH POLES A, P -
PUSHING THE ENERGY $|EB|^3 = |\bar{V}_x|^3$, UNIT
ENERGY, CUBE, INTO $|CD|^3 = 2 . |\bar{V}_x|^3$ CUBE.

1 = QUADRATURE
2 = **DUBLICATION** < 2 >

Figure-3-

In Fig. (1) The Spin $\bar{B} \equiv \text{Herpolhode} \equiv \bar{c}.\pi . |EC|^2$ of Photons is Transported as Velocity $\bar{R}O$
and is Analyzed as $\bar{v}_x = OG'$, $\bar{v}_y = RG$. At Point G' , the \bar{v}_y Vector Transfers the Energy of circle
 $\pi . |EC|^2$ Into the **UNIT Square** $CMNH$ such that $CMNH \equiv [EO]^2 \equiv \pi . |EC|^2$, **While** on (2) Poles
 A, P , of Vector \bar{v}_x , Forms The **UNIT- Meters** $CP \equiv OG'$ and CD , such that $[CD]^3 = 2 . [CP]^3$.

THE QUANTUM - CLONING UNIT-MOULD OF PHOTONS

THE ANGULAR MOMENTUM \bar{B} AS SPIN \bar{S} OF PHOTONS ON THE CONJUGATE CIRCLE [B, BE = EC] OF -- 2-Vectors 3-Poles R-Mechanism --

THE PROOF

> FROM Relation $Spin=S = \bar{w} \cdot \bar{B} / 2 = \bar{c} \cdot \bar{B} / 2r$
Then $\bar{c} = |2 \cdot r \cdot \bar{S} / \bar{B}| = \sqrt{\bar{C}_T^2 + \bar{C}_R^2}$ AND
AT POINT R, $\bar{C}_T = \bar{R}O = \sqrt{\bar{V}_x^2 + \bar{V}_y^2}$

> AT Point R, $|\bar{C}_T = \bar{R}O| = \sqrt{\bar{V}_x^2 + \bar{V}_y^2}$
Tangential Velocity $\bar{R}O$, ACTS AT Point G' , $-\bar{V}_x$ ON $\llcorner CC'$ Axis & $\bar{V}_y \perp$ ON CC' --
PUSHING CMNH, UNIT-Energy, SQUARE
Forming THE TORSIONAL ANGLE
 $\Phi = \bar{r} \cdot \bar{\Phi} = G' \bar{P}O = 2\pi / r^2$ Rads.

> FOR Point G' AT C' , Torsional Angle
 $\Phi = C' \bar{P}O = 2\pi / r^2 = 45^\circ$, which
is The Bellow Motion of Photon, AND
Energy-Square $CAC'P = CMNH \cdot CHH'M'$.

THE CUBS-UNIT-MOULD

$$[CD]^3 = 2 \cdot [CP]^3$$

$$[Z]^3 = 2 \cdot [X]^3 \text{ VECTOR } / X$$

THE ANGULAR MOMENTUM \bar{B} . AS
THE SPIN -- \bar{S} -- OF PHOTONS ON THE
2-Vectors 3-Poles Rotation- Mechanism -
BECOMES a)...THE UNIT - SQUARE =
 $CMNH = \pi \cdot |AC/2|^2$ b)...THE UNIT-CUBE
= $[CP]^3 = |EB|^3$, AND c)...THE
CLONING - UNIT CUBE = $[CD]^3 = 2 \cdot |EB|^3$

IN-(1)..THE SPIN { \bar{B} = THE CIRCLE
FROM HERPOLHODE = $\{c \cdot \pi \cdot |EC|^2\}$, OF
PHOTONS. AND IS TRANSPORTED AS
VELOCITY $\bar{R}O = \sqrt{\bar{V}_x^2 + \bar{V}_y^2}$ & ACTS
AT POINT G' , $-\bar{V}_x$ INTO, CC' AXIS
AND \bar{V}_y , ONTO, CC' AXIS --
PUSHING $CMNH$, UNIT-ENERGY,
SQUARE = $\pi \cdot |AC/2|^2$, FORMING TORSIONAL
ANGLE $\Phi = G' \bar{P}O = 2\pi / r^2$ Rads.

IN-(2)..THE VELOCITY VECTOR \bar{AB}
ACTS AT POINT B - WITH POLES A, P -
PUSHING THE ENERGY $|EB|^3 = |\bar{V}_x|^3$, UNIT
ENERGY, CUBE, INTO $[CD]^3 = 2 \cdot |\bar{V}_x|^3$ CUBE.

1 = QUADRATURE
2 = DUPLICATION

Figure-4-

In=(1)- The Spin $\bar{B} \equiv$
Herpolhode $\equiv \bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot |EC|^2$

of Photons is Transported
as Velocity $\bar{R}O$, and is
Analyzed as $\bar{v}_x = OG'$,
 $\bar{v}_y = RG$. At Point G' ,
the \bar{v}_y Vector Transfers the
Energy of circle $\pi \cdot |EC|^2$
Into Square CMNH such
that $CMNH \equiv [EO]^2$,

While In=(2)- From { The
2-Vectors, 2-Poles

Rotating The Poles A, P,
of Vector \bar{v}_x , Forms The
UNIT-Meters $CP \equiv OG'$
and CD, such that $[CD]^3$
 $= 2 \cdot [CP]^3$.

In=(3)- Are Formed, The 2-

Right Triangles, **PAD, PBD**

from {The 2-Vectors, 2Poles

Rotating Squares
Mechanism

On where valids the

Dublication of the Unequal
Vectors.

3.. Trisection. [46] =
Fig,31-32-333-34

This Problem follows the two Dimensional logic, where, **the Geometrical magnitudes and their unique circle**, have a linear relation (continuous Analogy) in all Spaces as, in one in two in three Dimensions, and as this happens to Compatible Coordinate Systems, happens also in Circle-arcs. The Compact-Logic-Space-Layer exists in Units, (**The case of 90° angle**), where then we may find a new machine that produces the 1/3 of angles as in F.11.[11]

Since angles can be Produced from any monad OB, and this because monad can formulate a circle of radius OB, and any Point A on circle can then formulate Angle < AOB, therefore the logic of continuous analogy of monads in all spaces issues also and on OA radius equal to OB.

Application in Physics :

According to math theory of Elasticity, the total work on free edges where there is no Shear becomes from Principal stresses only and work is $W = \frac{\sigma^2}{2E} + \frac{\tau^2}{2G}$ and the analogous Energy in Energy-monads $W = \frac{1}{2}[\epsilon E^2 + \mu H^2]$ spread in cave as the **First Harmonic** and equal to the Outer Spin $\bar{S} = E / w = 2\pi.r.c$. The Equation of Planck's Energy $E = h.f = (h/\lambda).c$, and is equal to the Isochromatic Pattern fringe-order in the New-monad as the difference, $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2 = (a/d).N = (a/d)n.f_1 = (8\pi r^2/3).n.f_1$, where n = the order of isochromatic, a number, f1 = the frequency of the Fundamental-Harmonic.

Since Total Energy in cave (wr)² is dependent on frequency only, and is stored in the Fundamental and the first Six Harmonics, so the Summations Bands of these Seven Isochromatic Quantized interference fringe-order-Patterns, is the Total Energy E in the same cave (wr)² as, Energy → $E = \text{Spin}.w = \bar{S}.w = (h/2\pi).2\pi f =$

$$= \left[\frac{8\pi r^2 f_1}{3} \right] \cdot \left[\frac{n(n+1)}{2} \right] = \left[\frac{4\pi r^2 f_1}{3} \right] n.(n+1) \dots\dots\dots(a)$$

When Stress (σ1-σ2) go up then, n = **order fringe defining Energy** goes up also, and the colors cycle through a more or less repeating Pattern and the Intensity of the colors diminishes. Since Phase $\phi = kx - \omega t = \text{Spatial and Time Oscillation dependence}$,

For n = 1, Energy in the First Harmonic is,

$E = 2\pi.r.c = \left[\frac{4\pi r^2}{3} \right].f_1$ [1], and for n = 2 Energy in the First and Second Isochromatic Harmonic is, $E = \left[\frac{4\pi r^2}{3} \right].f_1$ [3] in threes, and φ is trisected with Energy-Bunched variation f2, i.e. **The Energy stored in a Homogeneous resonance, is spread in the First of Seven-Harmonics beginning from the Fundamental and after the filling with frequency f1, follows the Second-Harmonic. In Second-Harmonic Energy as frequency is Doubled and this because of sufficient keeping Homogeneously in the Spatial dependence Quantity $kx = (2\pi/\lambda).x$ which is in threes, meaning that → Dipole – Energy is Spatially-trisected in Space-Quantity Quanta the Spin=h/2π as the angle φ, of Phase $\phi = kx - \omega t = (2\pi/\lambda).x$, and Bisected by the Energy-Quantity Quanta as in an RLC circuit. [49]**

Fig-11-A. → Presentation of the Trisection Method on Dr. Geo – Machine Macro – constructions.

4.. Parallel line. [124] = Fig ,8-

A line (*Two Points only*) is Not a Great circle (*more than three Points being in circle's Plane*) so Anything Built on this logic is a mislead false .The fact that the Sum of angles on any Triangle is 180° is springing for the first time , in Article (Rational Figured numbers or Figures) [9] .

Conclusions :

- 1.. From any Point M , there is only one Parallel to any A-B , Straight line .
- 2.. From Point M , there is only one Parallel to , A – B (when it goes $\rightarrow \infty$) , Straight line .
- 3.. From Point M , there is only one Parallel to , B – A (when it goes $\rightarrow \infty$) , Straight line .
- 4..The light-rays and consequently the Photons travel in Straight lines , **i.e. Photons follow** the Euclidean Geometry and NOT any other .
- 5..Time is the meter , to measure the changes in Energy = **motion** = Force x displacement , and NOT any other essence .

The essence of Universe is Space \equiv **Distance** $[\oplus \leftarrow r \rightarrow \ominus]$, Energy \equiv **motion** $[\oplus \sigma \ominus]$.

- 6..The Gravitational force G , causes the Bending of the light rays (of Photons) , and Not the warping of Spacetime , which meaning is Not existing Because this Concept has never been clarified .

This admission of two or more than two Parallel lines, instead of one of Euclid's, does not Proof the Truth of the admission. The same to Euclid's also , until the Present Proved method . Euclidean Geometry does not distinguish , Space from time Because time exists only in its Deviation - Plank's length level , neither Space from Energy - because Energy exists as **The Quanta** on any first Dimensional Unit AB , which as above connects the only two Fundamental Elements of Universe , that of Points or Sector = Segment = Monad = Quaternion , and that of Energy. [23]-[39].

The Proposed Method in articles , Based on the Prior four axioms only , PROOFS, (Not using any admission but a Pure Geometric logic under the Restrictions imposed to seek the solution) that , through Point M on any Plane ABM (three Points only that are not coinciding and which consist the Plane) , Passes only one line of which all Points equidistant from AB as Point M , i.e. the right is to Euclid Geometry.

The what is needed for conceiving the alterations from Points which are nothing , to Segments , **i.e.** quantization of Points as , *the discreteting = monads = quaternion* , to lines , Plane and Volume , is the acquiring and having Extrema knowledge .

In Euclidean Geometry the inner transformations exist as **Pure Points** , Segments , lines , Planes , Volumes, etc. as the Absolute Geometry is (*The Continuity of Points*) , automatically transformed through the three Basic Moulds (*the three Master moulds and Linear Transformations exist as one Quantization*) to Relative external transformations , which exist as the , **material** , Physical world of matter and Energy (*Discrete of Monads*) . [43-44]

The New Perception connecting the Relativistic Time and Einstein's Energy - is Now Refining Time and Dark -matter Force - clearly proves That Big -Bang have Never been existed .

In [17-45-46] is shown the most important **Extrema Geometrical Mechanism in this Cosmos** which is that of **STPL lines** , that Produces and composite , **All the Opposite Space Points** from Spaces to Anti-Spaces and to Sub-Spaces as this is in a Common Circle *this is the Sub-Space* , to lines into a Cylinder .**This extrema mould is a Transformation i.e. It is a Geometrical Quantization Mechanism** , \rightarrow for the Quantization of Euclidean geometry, *points* ,to the Physical world , **to Physics** , and is based on the following Geometrical logic , Since Primary Point ,A, is nothing and without direction and it is the only Space , and this Point to exist , **to be** , at any other Point ,B, which is not coinciding with Point ,A, then on this couple exists the Principle of Virtual Displacements $W = \int_A^B P. ds = 0$ or $[ds.(P_A+P_B) = 0]$, **i.e.** For any $ds > 0$ Impulse $\mathbf{P} = (\mathbf{P}_A + \mathbf{P}_B) = \mathbf{0}$ and Work $[ds .(\mathbf{P}_A + \mathbf{P}_B) = \mathbf{0}]$, **Therefore** , Each Unit $\mathbf{AB} = \mathbf{ds} > \mathbf{0}$, exists by this Inner Impulse (P) where $P_A + P_B = 0$. The Position and Dimension of all Points which are connected across the Universe and that of Spaces , exists , Because of this equilibrium Static Inner Impulse and thus **show the Energy-Space continuum** .

Applying the above logic on any Monad = Quaternion $(s + \bar{v} \cdot \nabla i)$, where, s = the Real Part and $(\bar{v} \cdot \nabla i)$ the Imaginary Part of quaternion so, Thrust of two equal and Opposite Quaternion is the **Action of these Quaternions which is**,

$$(s + \bar{v} \cdot \nabla i) \cdot (s + \bar{v} \cdot \nabla i) = [s + \bar{v} \cdot \nabla i]^2 = s^2 + |\bar{v}|^2 \cdot \nabla i^2 + 2|s| |\bar{v}| \cdot \nabla i = s^2 - |\bar{v}|^2 + 2|s| |\bar{v}| \cdot \bar{r} \therefore$$

$$|\nabla i = [s^2] - [|\bar{v}|^2] + [2\bar{w} \cdot |s| |\bar{r}| \cdot \nabla i] \quad \text{where,}$$

$[+s^2] \rightarrow s^2 = (w \cdot r)^2$, \rightarrow is the **Real Part** of the new Quaternion which is, the **Positive**

Scalar Product, of Space from the same scalar Product, s, s with $\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2}, \dots$, **Spin** and this because of w , and which represents the massive, Space, Part of Quaternion \rightarrow monad. $[-s^2] \rightarrow -|\bar{v}|^2 = -|\bar{w} \cdot \bar{r}|^2 = -[|\bar{w}| \cdot |\bar{r}|]^2 = -(w \cdot r)^2 \rightarrow$ is the always, the **Negative** Scalar Product, of **Anti-space** from the dot product of \bar{w}, \bar{r} vectors, with $-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{3}{2}$, Spin and this because of $-w$, and which represents the massive, **Anti-Space**, Part of quaternion \rightarrow monad. $[\nabla i] \rightarrow 2 \cdot |s| \times |\bar{w} \cdot \bar{r}| \therefore |\nabla i| = 2|w \cdot r| \cdot (w \cdot r) \cdot \nabla i = 2 \cdot (w \cdot r)^2 \rightarrow$ is a **Vector** of, the velocity vector Product, from the cross Product of \bar{w}, \bar{r} vectors with Double Angular velocity term giving 1,3,5, Spin and this because of $\pm w$, in inner structure of monads, and represents the, **Energy Quanta**, of the Unification of the Space and Anti-Space through the Energy (*Work*) Part of Quaternion.

A wider analysis in article [40-43]

When a Point, A , is quantized to Point, B , then becomes the line segment $AB =$ Vector $AB =$ Quaternion $[AB] \rightarrow$ monad, and is the closed System, A, B , **and since** also from the law of conservation of Energy, *it is the first law of Thermodynamics*, which states that the Energy of a closed System remains constant, therefore *neither increases nor Decreases without interference from outside*, and so the Total amount of Energy in this closed system, AB , in existence has always been the same, **Then** the Forms that this Energy takes are constantly changing, **i.e.**

The conservation of Energy is realized when Stored in Monads and following the Physical laws in E-geometry where then are Material \rightarrow Points, monads, etc \leftarrow . **This is the Unification of this Physical world of, what is called matter and Energy, and that of Euclidean Geometry which are, Points, Segments, Planes and Volumes.**

For more in [48].

The Three Moulds (i.e. The three Geometrical Mechanism) of Euclidean Geometry which create the METERS of monads and which are, *Linear* for a Perpendicular Segment, *Plane* for the Square equal to the circle on Segment, *Space* for the Double Volume of initial volume of the Segment, (*the volume of the sphere is related to Plane which is related to line and which is related to segment*), **Exist on Segments** in Spaces, Anti-spaces and Sub-spaces.

This is the Euclidean Geometry Quantization to its constituents (i.e. Geometry in its moulds). The analogous happens when E-Geometry is Quantized to Space and Energy monads [48].

METER of Points A is the Point A , the METER of line is the Segment $ds = AB =$ monad = constant and equal to monad, or to the Perpendicular distance of this segment to the set of two Parallel lines between Points A, B , the METER of Plane

is that of circle on Segment = monad and which is that Square equal to the circle, number π , the METER of Volume $^3\sqrt{2}$, is that of Cube, on Segment = monad which is equal to the Double Cube of the Segment and Measures all the Spaces, the Anti-spaces and the Subspaces in this cosmos. Generally is more referred,

a). There is **not any Paradoxes of the infinite** because is clearly defined what is a Point a cave and what is a Segment.

b). **The Algebra of constructible numbers and number Fields is an Absurd Theory**

Based on Groundless Axioms as the Fields are, and with Direction the Non-Euclid Orientations Purposes which must Be Properly Revised.

c). **The Algebra of Transcendental Numbers has been devised to Postpone the Pure Geometrical thought**, which is the base of all sciences, by changing the Base-Field of solutions to Algebra as

Base . Pythagorians Discovered the existence of the incommensurable of the diagonal of a square in relation to its side without giving up the Base , which was and is the geometrical logic.

d). All Theories concerning *the Unsolvability of the Special Greek Problems are Based on Cantor's shady Proof* , < *that the Totality of All Algebraic Numbers is Denumerable* > and Not Edified on the Geometrical Basic logic which is the foundations of all Algebra .

The Problem of Doubling the cube F-1-2-3 , as that of the Trisection of any angle F-33, is a Mechanical Problem and could not be seen differently and the Proposed Geometrical solutions is clearly exposed to the Critic of all Readers .

All trials for Squaring the circle are shown in [44] and the set questions will be answered on the Changeable System of the two Expanding Squares ,*Translation [T] and Rotation [R]* . The solution of Squaring the circle using the Plane Procedure method is now Presented in F-1,2 , and consists an , *Overthrow* , to all existing Theories in Geometry , Physics and Philosophy .

e). Geometry is the Base of all sciences and it is the reflective logic from the Objective reality , which is Nature , to our mind . (markos 30/10/2015)

The locus of all these Points is a straight line.

Figure – 8 - : The Three Points .

The main Question should be for EPR and for all arguing an Answer to the following .

Which Geometry Do , light-rays , follow ???

The Euclidean-Geometry EG \equiv Light ray $\rightarrow \bar{v} \cdot [\bar{f}_n] + f_n \equiv$ Straight line $\equiv \bar{v} \cdot [f_n]$

The Hyperbolic-Geometry HG \equiv Light ray $\rightarrow \bar{v} \cdot [\bar{f}_n] + f_n \equiv$ A Circle $\equiv [\bar{f}_n]$

The Riemannian-Geometry RG \equiv Light ray $\rightarrow \bar{v} \cdot [\bar{f}_n] + f_n \equiv$ A Line-Vector $\equiv \bar{v} \cdot [\bar{f}_n]$

The Material-Geometry MG \equiv Light ray \rightarrow A Line-Vector in Energy-Caves , and a Straight line to Infinite as the diagrams of the Stationary-Wave-crest-Wavelength λ .

$[\oplus \leftarrow \lambda \rightarrow \ominus] \rightarrow \lambda \leftarrow [\oplus \leftarrow \lambda \rightarrow \ominus] \equiv \bar{v} \cdot [\bar{f}_n] + f_n$ with Wavelength $[\bar{v} \cdot \bar{f}_n] \rightarrow [\bar{v} = \bar{c} = \lambda \frac{f}{\phi}]$

[MG] [MG] [MG] \rightarrow The Dual-Nature of Light-Photon has the

Answer in [92] In this , answer is left to the Reader \rightarrow Markos Georgallides 25/9/2020 \leftarrow

Material - Geometry Particle-Light-Ray is $[\oplus \leftarrow \lambda \rightarrow \ominus] \rightarrow \lambda \leftarrow [\oplus \leftarrow \lambda \rightarrow \ominus]$, i.e. \overrightarrow{AB} line Vector of Two Points only is the Light Ray such for *Cave-Vector* $\bar{v} \cdot [\bar{f}_n]$, as for *Wave-Vector* $[\bar{v} \cdot f_n]$ on Straight-lines to infinity and is the Geometry followed from Zero-Point to Infinite

Because Space \equiv Electric-Field , Anti-Space \equiv Magnetic-Field , Energy \equiv Motion ,

Quantization is a Necessity in Nature and Electromagnetic-Radiation ,is the Only Complex Way of motion and for the Energy , which is motion , is to Travel and Composited in Caves .

(markos 30 / 05 / 2026)

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Article [125] is Dedicated to the **National Technical University of Athens** , NTUA , from where I Graduated and Acquired the Path Knowledge of the Truths of Nature..

Το Άρθρο [125] είναι Αφιερωμένο στο Εθνικό Μετσόβιο Πολυτεχνείο (ΕΜΠ) , από όπου Αποφοίτησα και απέκτησα την Ατραπό της Γνώσης των Αληθειών της Φύσης.

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